

**KAMPALA INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY (KIU) WESTERN CAMPUS (WC)
RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE (REC)**

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INFORMED CONSENT DOCUMENT

This document aims to clearly outline the research study and the related expectations for potential participants. It should be written in lay terms; and typed on KIU WC REC letterhead. The wording should be directed to the research participant, NOT to the REC. If a technical term must be used, it should be defined/explained the first time it is applied. Similarly, abbreviation should be written out in full when first used.

NB: When completed, all the sections of this document must not show any edits or deletions. The typing font used in the responses on the form should differ from that of the questions.

Study Title :

CORPORATE CULTURE AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENTS IN WESTERN UGANDA

Principal Investigator(s): ASIIMWE AISHA

PhD PAM/8172/163/DU

INTRODUCTION

What you should know about this study

- You are being asked to join a research study;
- This consent form explains the research study and your part in the study;
- Please read it carefully; and take as much time as you need;
- You are a volunteer. You can choose not to take part; and if you join, you may quit at any time. There will be no penalty if you decide to leave the study.

Leave blank (for REC Office only):

NAME OF REC CHAIR: *Prof. Ahmed Kiswezi*

TELEPHONE: **+256 772426581**

KIU REC STAMP:

For REC Office use only:

APPROVAL DATE:

APPROVED CONSENT REC VERSION NUMBER:

PI's NAME:

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Provide a brief background to the study here.

This study is entitled “Corporate Culture and Employee Performance in selected local Governments in Western Uganda “this current study is going to take place in Kasese and Kabarole districts local governments in Western Uganda.

Purpose of the research project

Include a statement that the study involves research, estimated number of participants, an explanation of the purpose(s) of the research procedure, and the expected duration of the participant's participation.

The researcher shall consider 155 participants and will present a letter from Kampala International University and permit from the National council for Science and Technology to Kasese and Kabarole district local government authorities for permission to go ahead with the study and the participants shall fill in the questionnaire for two days.

Why you are being asked to participate

The participant is asked participate because he/she has valuable information the study can consider in order to improve on employee performance in Kasese and Kabarole districts local governments

Procedures:

Provide a description of the procedures to be followed; and identification of any procedures that are experimental, clinical, etc. If there is need for storage of biological (body) specimens, please explain why. Include a statement requesting for consent to store the specimens, and state the duration of storage. *N/A*

Risks/Discomforts

There are no anticipated risks from participating in the study. The participants can be assured that no harm or discomfort will result from participating in this proposed study.

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Benefits

The study participants especially the Administrators will indirectly benefit from the study findings if the developed model for employee performance is adopted by the local government. All employees in the twelve departments at each local government will benefit from improved performance which will be supported by the developed model.

Incentives/Rewards for Participating

Every participant will be compensated for participating in the study with a monetary fee of 20,000/= Uganda shillings only. Therefore with a total number of 155 participants, three million, one hundred thousand shillings (3100, 000/=) will be put aside to cater for the compensation of research participants.

Protecting data confidentiality

All information gathered by this research will be kept anonymous and confidential. All information taken from the study will be coded to protect each participant's name. No names or other identifying information will be used when discussing or reporting data. The principal Investigator will safely keep all files and data collected in a secured manner. Once the data has been fully analyzed the questionnaires will be destroyed.

However, local Research Ethics Committee (REC) and Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) are the only entities which may have access to private information that identifies the research participants by name.

Protecting participant privacy during data collection

Describe how this will be ensured.

The Self-administered Structured questionnaires shall only bare the initials the names but not the full names of the respondents in order to protect their privacy.

Right to refuse/withdraw

Include a statement that participation is voluntary; and refusal to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits to which the participant is, otherwise, entitled.

Participation in this study is voluntary and any participant who is not comfortable with the kind of data being asked in the study can choose to withdraw at any time without any penalty this participant will still benefit from this study.

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What happens if you leave the study?

The participant may discontinue participation at any time, without penalty or loss of benefits.

Who do I ask/call if I have questions or a problem?

Please contact the KIU REC Office for any questions/problem on the addressed indicated below:

The KIU REC Chair

P.o Box 71, Bushenyi

Mobile: +256-772426581

Email: kiurec2017@kiu.ac.ug

Principal Investigator(s) contact and Email: ASIIMWE AISHA.....0701133776

asiimwe.aisha@kiu.ac.ug

What does your signature (or thumb print/mark) on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that you have:

- Been informed about this study’s purpose, procedures, and possible benefits and risks;
- Been given the chance to ask questions before you sign; and
- Voluntarily agreed to be in this study.

Name of participant

Signature of participant

Thumb print

Date

Name of person obtaining Consent

Signature

Thumb print

Date

<p>Leave blank (for REC Office only): NAME OF REC CHAIR: Prof. Ahmed Kiswezi TELEPHONE: +256 772426581 KIU REC STAMP:</p>	<p>For REC <input type="text"/></p> <p>APPROVAL DATE: APPROVED CONSENT REC VERSION NUMBER: PI’s NAME: REC NO: UG-REC- 023</p>
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Names of witness

Signature of witness

Thumb print

Date

Leave blank (for REC Office only):

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